

Decoding Regulatory structure from RNA-seq Data: A Reproducible Python Framework for Gene Regulatory Network Inference Using GENIE3

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Abstract

In modern biology gene expression profiling using RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) has become a major tool. Still most analyses remain limited to identifying differentially expressed genes. Although being informative, such approaches do not reveal the regulatory mechanisms that facilitates gene expression programs. In such a scenario Gene Regulatory Networks (GRNs) plays an important role. It provides a systems-level structure to uncover these mechanisms by modelling the interaction between transcription factors and their downstream targets. This work presents a practical computational pipeline for inferring GRNs from RNA-seq data using the GENIE3 algorithm. Which is a tree-based method that influence Random Forest models in estimating regulatory interactions (Huynh-Thu et al., 2010). The presented pipeline integrates data preprocessing, transcription factor selection, model execution and network construction into a reproducible Python-based workflow using the arboreto library (Moerman et al., 2019). In addition to this, the study also provides a conceptual insight into GRN inference. It further discusses common pitfalls, and shows how to identify major regulators from inferred networks. Publication-style figures are included to illustrate each stage of the pipeline. All scripts, example datasets, and figure-generation resources are provided to support reproducibility.

KEYWORDS

Gene Regulatory Networks; RNA-seq; GENIE3; Systems Biology; Computational Biology; Machine Learning; Network Inference; Transcription Factors

1.Introduction

RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) has increasingly modified our way to quantify gene expression at large scale. However, most analytical workflows remain focused on differential expression analysis. Although it identifies genes that change under various conditions, it does not explain the regulatory logic behind these changes (Love et al., 2014; Robinson et al., 2010). Biological systems are by nature regulatory. Gene expression is controlled by complex interactions between transcription factors and their target genes, which forms a structured networks that govern cellular behavior. Understanding these networks is important for interpreting mechanisms of disease, development, and cellular differentiation. Gene Regulatory Networks (GRNs) provide a structure to model these interactions. In a GRN, nodes represent genes and edges represent regulatory relationships. Identifying these interactions from expression data remains a central challenge in systems biology. Several computational approaches have been proposed for GRN inference. These approaches include mutual information-based methods such as ARACNE (Margolin et al., 2006), Bayesian network approaches (Friedman et al., 2000) and correlation-based frameworks such as WGCNA (Langfelder & Horvath, 2008).

Among these, GENIE3 has emerged as one of the most widely accepted methods. It is consistently performing well in benchmark challenges (Huynh-Thu et al., 2010). GENIE3 structures GRN inference as a series of supervised learning problems. It uses Random Forest models to predict gene expression based on selected regulators. This allows it to capture non-linear reliance without needing strong prior assumptions about regulatory mechanisms. This study presents a practical and reproducible pipeline for GRN inference using GENIE3 in Python. The goal is not to introduce a new algorithm, but to provide a structured pipeline that integrates biological reasoning with machine learning implementation. Therefore, enabling researchers to extract regulatory insights from RNA-seq data efficiently.

2. Methods

2.1 Data Preparation

The data can be normalized for RNA-seq expression matrices using approaches such as TPM, CPM, or variance-stabilized counts to account for sequencing depth and technical variability (Love et al., 2014; Robinson et al., 2010). Low-expression genes are filtered to reduce noise and to improve model stability.

2.2 Transcription Factor Selection

A list of curated transcription factors is used as selected regulators. This reduces dimensionality and improves interpretability by restricting the model to biologically important regulatory interactions.

2.3 GRN Inference Using GENIE3

The GENIE3 algorithm models each gene as a function of transcription factor expression using Random Forest regression (Huynh-Thu et al., 2010). For each target gene, a predictive model is trained, and feature related scores were extracted for all selected regulators. These feature scores are aggregated across all genes to generate a ranked list of regulatory interactions. The process used in this pipeline is provided by the arboreto library, which enables scalable computation (Moerman et al., 2019).

2.4 Network Construction

Edges are ranked by featured scores, and a subset of top-ranked interactions is maintained to construct a small regulatory network. This step is necessary to reduce noise and focus on the most biologically meaningful interactions.

2.5 Hub Gene Identification

Node degree, particularly outgoing edges from transcription factors, is used to identify hub genes. These highly connected nodes represent selected major regulators that may control large transcriptional programs.

3. Workflow Overview

The practical implementation of this pipeline consists of the following steps, a) normalization of RNA-seq expression data, b) filtering of low-expression genes, c) selection of curated transcription factor regulators, d) GRN inference using GENIE3 or GRNBoost2, e) ranking of TF–target interactions, f) construction of regulatory networks g) identification of candidate master regulators, h) publication-style visualization and downstream interpretation.

4. Discussion

GENIE3 provides a flexible and powerful structure for GRN inference, particularly due to its ability to model non-linear relationships between regulators and targets. Unlike correlation-based approaches such as WGCNA (Langfelder & Horvath, 2008), GENIE3 explicitly models predictive relationships. Therefore, offering a more mechanistic interpretation of gene regulation. However, it is important to note that GENIE3 does not establish causality. The inferred relationships are based on statistical output and therefore should be interpreted as selected regulatory interactions. Experimental validation, such as ChIP-seq or perturbation-based studies, is required to confirm these predictions. Though advances in single-cell analysis have out reached GRN inference approaches through methods such as SCENIC, which integrates GENIE3-based inference with motif analysis and clustering (Aibar et al., 2017). Additionally, implementations of GRNBoost2 enable faster analysis of large single-cell datasets (Moerman et al., 2019).

5. Conclusion

The RNA-seq dataset contains more than expression measurements information. Which encodes an underlying regulatory framework that governs cellular behavior. GRN inference methods such as GENIE3 enable researchers to move beyond gene lists and toward a systems-level understanding of gene regulation. By integrating biological knowledge with machine learning, this pipeline can provide a practical approach for reconstructing regulatory networks and identifying key transcriptional regulators. This therefore, represents an important step toward bridging the gap between high-throughput data generation and mechanistic biological insight.

6. Software Availability

All Python scripts, example datasets, publication-style figures, and documentation associated with this framework are available through the accompanying Zenodo repository.

7. Disclaimer

This work is a methodological and educational resource and does not present novel experimental findings. The inferred regulatory relationships are based on computational predictions and require experimental validation.

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